

Cryoprotectant treatment and cryopreservation of the marine dinoflagellate *Breviolum* sp.

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Abstract

Dinoflagellates are among the most ecologically diverse group of microalgae. Dinoflagellate species from the family Symbiodiniaceae form endosymbiotic associations with invertebrates, such as corals, sea anemones, and jellyfish. Strains of dinoflagellates are maintained alive in culture collections worldwide. This is labor-intensive, expensive, and there is a risk of contamination or genetic drift. Cryopreserving these strains will help to maintain long-term viability, molecular integrity and to reduce costs. In this study, we explored the effect of cryoprotectant agents (CPAs) and freezing methods on *Breviolum* sp. A total of 12 CPAs were assessed at concentrations between 5 - 15%, as well as in combination with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and other non-penetrating CPAs. Two freezing techniques were employed: rapid freezing and controlled-rate freezing. *Breviolum* sp. was successfully cryopreserved using 15% DMSO. For *Breviolum* sp. there was higher cell viability ($45.4 \pm 2.2\%$) when using the controlled-rate freezing compared to the rapid freezing technique ($10.0 \pm 2.8\%$). This optimized cryopreservation protocol will be of benefit for the cryopreservation of other species from the family Symbiodiniaceae.

Keywords: Microalgae, dinoflagellates, Symbiodiniaceae, cryopreservation, cryoprotectant agents, HABs

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Introduction

Dinoflagellates are motile unicellular algae that are important contributors to primary production in aquatic and marine habitats (Bravo and Figueroa, 2014). Dinoflagellate species from the family Symbiodiniaceae exist in symbiotic relationships with many invertebrates including corals, sea anemones, jellyfish, giant clams, flatworms, and benthic foraminifera (LaJeunesse, 2020; Pochon and LaJeunesse, 2021). They are important for research and studies on the mechanisms of rapid adaptation or acclimatization to environmental changes in corals given the impact of increased sea surface temperatures (Rouzé *et al.*, 2019).

To protect and preserve valuable dinoflagellate species, cryopreservation has been suggested as the most reliable technique to ensure their long-term genetic stability and to reduce storage and regular maintenance costs (Rhodes *et al.*, 2006; Hagedorn and Carter, 2015). However, attempts to have a well-optimized and uniform cryopreservation protocol that can be applied to all microalgae has been unsuccessful (Youn and Hur, 2009). The successful cryopreservation of *Breviolum* sp. would protect its genetic composition, allow easy access for research use, and reduce the risk of contamination during repeated sub-culturing. This study aimed to identify optimal freezing and thawing conditions to enhance the survival of this marine dinoflagellate following cryopreservation.

Materials and Methods

Isolate and culture conditions

The dinoflagellate culture *Breviolum* sp. (CAWD197) was obtained from the

Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae (CICCM; <http://cultures.cawthron.org.nz/ciccm/>). Cells were grown in f/2/L1 growth medium (Guillard, 1975; Guillard and Hargraves, 1993) at 25 °C in a 12:12 light: dark cycle under 100 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ photosynthetically active radiation (PAR).

Types and combinations of cryoprotectant agents

The cryoprotectant agents (CPAs) used were: DMSO (Purity GC \geq 99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich, Japan), Methanol (MeOH; HPLC grade, \geq 99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany), Glycerol (Sigma-Aldrich, Malaysia), Propylene glycol (PG; Sigma-Aldrich, Singapore), Diethylene glycol (DEG; Sigma-Aldrich, U.S.A.), Ethylene glycol (EG; spectrophotometric grade, \geq 99%, Sigma-Aldrich, Malaysia), Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP; Sigma-Aldrich, U.S.A.) and Polyethylene glycol (PEG; Sigma-Aldrich, Germany). Single CPA solutions were prepared in sterilized growth medium to give final concentrations of 5%, 8%, 10%, 12%, and 15% (v/v or w/v). For combined CPA treatments, DMSO was used at a ratio of 1:1 with the non-penetrating compounds proline (Sigma-Aldrich, U.S.A.), sucrose (BDH, England), sorbitol (Sigma-Aldrich, U.S.A.), and glucose (BDH, England).

CPA treatment experiments

An aliquot (1 mL) of each culture was pipetted into 12-well plates (Costar, China). For each species, 100 μL aliquots of the CPAs were added to the wells with gentle agitation (10 min, Room temperature (RT), 30 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PAR) between each addition until a final 1:1 dilution was obtained. The CPA-

treated cultures were left to equilibrate in complete darkness (30 min, RT). *Breviolum* sp. was maintained at 25 °C, under controlled minimal light (56 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ PAR). After incubation for one week with different CPAs, dinoflagellate cells were categorized and enumerated as either healthy, unhealthy, or dead based on changes in the chlorophyll pigmentation as observed using an inverted microscope (Olympus CK X41 Tokyo, Japan).

Freezing techniques

1. *Rapid freezing technique*: The cultures were aspirated into cryopreservation straws (0.5 cc, IMV, France) and the straws were arranged horizontally on a metal rack fitted onto polystyrene floats. The rack (41x 14 x 4 cm, l x w x h) and was placed gently over a liquid nitrogen bath (45 x 30 x 6 cm, l x w x h) to induce rapid freezing of the cells before finally plunging the straws into liquid nitrogen.

2. *Controlled-rate freezing technique*: The cultures were aspirated into cryopreservation straws which were transferred to a controlled-rate freezer (Cryologic Pty, Mt Waverley, Australia). The freezer was programmed to cool from 20 °C to -40 °C at a rate of 1 °C min^{-1} . The straws were held at -40 °C for 10 min before plunging into liquid nitrogen.

The straws were kept frozen under liquid nitrogen for a period of one week.

Thawing procedure

Thawing was carried out by plunging the straws into a water bath (20 °C). Fresh media was added to the thawed cultures which were kept under dark conditions at 20 °C RT for 24 h, followed by 48 h under 27 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$

of red light (OSRAM L18W/60, Germany) to facilitate the recovering of the cells. Finally, fresh media (40 mL) was added into the plastic vessels (70 mL Labserv, Thermofisher Scientific NZ) and the *Breviolum* sp. cultures were transferred to their normal standard light conditions for growth.

Results and Discussion

In single CPA treatments, at 5% final CPA concentration, DMSO, PVP and EG had >90% of cells surviving. Increasing the CPA concentration to 8%, 83.0 \pm 3.0% of the cells survived in DMSO while in PVP, 97.0 \pm 1.0% of the cells survived and EG had the lowest cell survival at 11.3 \pm 0%. At 10% concentration, DMSO treatment had 13.0 \pm 2.0% of the cells surviving while PVP had 81.0 \pm 2.0% and no cells survived in the EG treatment. At 12% concentration, only PVP treatment had cells surviving (21.7 \pm 1.2%), while one week incubation of the cells at 15% final CPA concentration resulted to no viable cells. During cryopreservation, a range of different single CPAs and different concentrations of combined CPAs commonly used to treat the cells before the freezing experiments (Hubálek, 2003). In this study, *Breviolum* sp. cells were treated with eight different single CPAs with concentrations varying between 5% and 15%. The selected single CPAs for the cryopreservation of *Breviolum* sp. were PVP (final concentrations of 5%, 8% and 10%) followed by EG and DMSO final concentrations of 5% and 8%, respectively. After the CPA treatment and incubation period, the preferred CPAs with the least impact on cells health was DMSO. DMSO was preferred because it penetrates cell membranes easily, can be removed from the cells, and did not support bacterial

contaminations (Taylor and Fletcher, 1999; Stock *et al.*, 2018).

For the combined CPAs, 5% sorbitol + 5% DMSO and 8% sorbitol + 5% DMSO were selected as the preferred combined CPAs for subsequent cryopreservation trials. However, the application of combined CPAs resulted in bacterial overgrowth in initial tests with all the treatments. The CPAs that encouraged bacterial contaminations were glycerol, PEG, PG and PVP. During cryopreservation, presence of high bacterial contaminations following CPA treatment can negatively influence the growth and recovery of cells (Visch *et al.*, 2019).

From the single CPAs selected and tested during the freezing experiments, 15% DMSO gave the best results with high cell viabilities in *Breviolum* sp. after thawing. Very low cell viabilities were observed when 15% EG was used as the CPA during the freezing experiments. The differences in cell viabilities from the two CPAs could be due to the different cryoprotective efficiencies in this species, with DMSO being the more favorable CPA (Hubálek, 2003). The combined CPAs used in this study did not yield any successful results for *Breviolum* sp. This might have been because the 30 minutes pre-incubation period that was used did not allow sufficient time for the combined CPAs to penetrate into the cells and thus, reduce the amount of water forming damaging ice crystals during freezing. Incubating the cells with CPA for a short period may be ineffective and, on the other hand, long exposure to CPAs may lead to toxicity in the cells (Taylor and Fletcher, 1999).

The two freezing techniques used to cryopreserve *Breviolum* sp. were rapid freezing and controlled-rate freezing. During rapid freezing, the cells viability was $10.0 \pm 2.8\%$ in 15% DMSO. When 15% EG was used, the cell viability was $2.0 \pm 0.7\%$ (Fig. 1).

For the controlled-rate freezing technique, *Breviolum* sp. was successfully cryopreserved with the highest cell viability of $45.4 \pm 2.2\%$ in 15% DMSO. When 15% EG was used the cell viability was $17.4 \pm 1.2\%$ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Cell viabilities of *Breviolum* sp. after rapid freezing technique using dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and ethylene glycol (EG) as cryoprotectant agents (CPAs). The cell viabilities are mean percentages of three replicates with error bars as standard deviation (SD).

Fig. 2. Cell viabilities of *Breviolum* sp. after controlled-rate freezing using dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and ethylene glycol (EG) as cryoprotectant agents (CPAs). The cell viabilities are the mean percentage of three replicates with error bars as standard deviation (SD).

From the two freezing techniques used in this study, the best cryopreservation technique that had the highest survival rate after thawing *Breviolum* sp. was the controlled-rate freezer using 15% DMSO as the CPA (Fig. 2), and the cells took one week to recover and divide. The optimized cryopreservation protocol described in this study may also enhance the cryopreservation of other species in the family Symbiodiniaceae and this is being investigated. This will protect the genetic integrity of these species for future research aiming to facilitate coral restoration efforts following extensive coral bleaching and habitat destruction.

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